

Effect of carbon doping on F-type defects in YAG and YAG:Ce crystals

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Ce-doped yttrium aluminum garnet (YAG) is among the efficient rare-earth garnet scintillators and phosphors. This paper addresses a computational and experimental study of complex F-type defect centers formed in YAG by doping with cerium and carbon. The formation energies determined by *ab initio* calculations of different defects and atomic chemical potentials in YAG:Ce,C are discussed in O-poor and O-rich conditions corresponding to the crystal growth under Ar+CO reducing atmosphere, and post-growth annealing in air. It is shown that as-grown crystals contain numerous positively charged defects responsible for F-type center formation, whereas mainly negative charged defects are remained after the annealing in air. The negatively charged defects located nearby Ce luminescence center occupying Y site may stabilize cerium in the tetravalent state and promote a hole transport to this luminescence center. This describes a high scintillation

efficiency of Ce,C-doped garnets. Furthermore, YAG:C and YAG:Ce,C with a high carbon concentration, besides of luminescence peaked at 400 ns ascribed to F^+ -type centers, possess a fast luminescence peaked around 650 nm that may be attributed to the complex defect centers. These unveiled features of the luminescence process in rare-earth garnets may contribute to the development of efficient luminescence materials.

1. Introduction

Rare earth garnet crystals are popular hosts for laser materials (at Nd-, Er-, Yb-doping), scintillators and phosphors (at Ce-, Pr-, Sc-doping), which are characterized by a high concentration of intrinsic defects, such as point defects and “antisites” (rare earth atoms occupying Al^{3+} sites).^[1, 2] Low formation energies of antisites and oxygen vacancies in YAG were determined by ab initio calculations in many works, see, for example.^[3, 4] Recently, we have introduced carbon-doped garnet scintillators, which possess specific optical and scintillation properties, such as a fast scintillation decay of 5 ns in YAG:C, irreversible discoloration in both types crystals after thermal annealing.^[5-7] Furthermore, it was recently shown that light yield in YAG:Ce,C tends to increase up to ca. 30000 phot MeV^{-1} with optimization of cerium and carbon concentrations.^[7]

Impact of carbon on defect structure in lutetium oxyorthosilicate, $Lu_2SiO_5:Ce$, another oxide scintillator, was studied in.^[8] Importantly, it was shown that C defects strongly interact with nearby oxygen vacancies and Ce, and C doping affects the amount of the oxygen vacancies and Ce^{4+} in Lu_2SiO_5 . Furthermore, C-doping introduced defect bands in the band gap of Lu_2SiO_5 with the energies ranging from 0.13 eV to 2.1 eV above the valence band maximum. Following the formation energies of point and complex defects in YAG:C determined in,^[9] in this work this approach is extended to carbon-related defects in YAG:Ce,C. Impact of these defects to the scintillation process is discussed in combination with optical spectroscopy data.

2. Results

2.1. Bond lengths and energies of C-related defects in YAG:Ce,C

In the considered local structures (**Figure 1**), the Ce atom is 8-fold coordinated by the O atoms with an average bond length of 2.46 Å for the Ce_Y (Table 1), being larger than the calculated value of 2.40 Å for the Y-O bond in the perfect YAG structure because of larger ionic radii of Ce^{3+} . Other nearby C defects increase the Ce-O bond distance even more (only nearest carbon is considered). The C-O bond length is calculated to be 1.43 Å and 2.06 Å for the C atom at the 4-fold and 6-fold coordinated Al sites, respectively, which is shorter than the Al-O bond length with values of 1.78 Å and 1.94 Å, reflecting stronger interaction between C and O, especially in the 4-fold coordination. The Ce-C bond for the C_O+Ce_Y is slightly longer than the Ce-O bond.

Figure 1. Local structures of the isolated substitutional Ce at the Y site (Ce_Y) and the complex defects consisting of Ce at the Y site and C at the O (C_O+Ce_Y), Al ($C_{Al-4}+Ce_Y$ and

$C_{Al-6+Ce_Y}$), and interstitial (C_i+Ce_Y) sites. The Ce, O and C atoms are labeled by green, red, and black color, respectively.

Table 1. Average Ce-O (d_{Ce-O}), C-O (d_{C-O}), and Ce-C (d_{Ce-C}) bond length (in Å) for Ce at the Y site and C at the O, Al, and interstitial sites.

	Ce_Y	C_{O+Ce_Y}	$C_{Al-4+Ce_Y}$	$C_{Al-6+Ce_Y}$	C_i+Ce_Y
d_{Ce-O}	2.46	2.48	2.50	2.47	2.51
d_{C-O}	—	—	1.43	2.06	2.25
d_{Ce-C}	—	2.50	—	—	—

Stability of the isolated and complex Ce defects is determined by the formation energy, as shown in **Figure 2**. The Ce_Y shows neutral charge state for the Fermi level ranging from 0.04 eV to the bottom of the conduction band (**Figure 3**) leading to instability of Ce^{4+} in the lattice. Overall, the formation energies in the O-poor limit are lower than those in the O-rich limit, which predicts higher concentration of Ce^{3+} in reducing atmosphere. The complex Ce defects containing C at the Al sites have lower formation energies than the isolated Ce defect in the O-rich limit. The C_{O+Ce_Y} is more stable than the $C_{Al-4+Ce_Y}$ and the $C_{Al-6+Ce_Y}$ in the O-poor limit when the Fermi level is below 5.40 eV. The interstitial C suppresses nearby Ce_Y .

The $C_{Al-4+Ce_Y}$ defects introduce the transition levels ($\epsilon(+/-)$, $\epsilon(-/-2)$, and $\epsilon(-2/-3)$) at 4.16, 4.50, and 4.54 eV, respectively, above the valence band maximum, while the transition levels ($\epsilon(+/0)$ and $\epsilon(0/-4)$) at 3.05 and 3.48 eV are found for the $C_{Al-6+Ce_Y}$ defects. The $\epsilon(+4/0)$ for the C_{O+Ce_Y} is located at 2.18 eV. The C doping would increase the concentration of Ce, although this has not been confirmed in the recent experiment.^[7]

Figure 2. Formation energies of the isolated and complex Ce defects as function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits. The charge states of the defects are represented by the slopes of the segments.

Figure 3. Thermodynamic transition levels of isolated and complex Ce defects.

2.2. Density of states and charge densities of C-related defects in YAG:Ce,C

Figure 4 illustrates the density of states for the isolated and complex Ce defects and spatial distribution of the defect states. **C atom at the O site introduces some extra occupied and unoccupied states in the band gap. Similar results were obtained in Lu₂SiO₅ doped with C, see .^[8]** The C_O+Ce_Y introduces some occupied states at 0.37, 0.58, 0.73, and 0.95 eV and unoccupied states at 2.35 and 2.83 eV as compared to the Ce_Y. The occupied states are mainly contributed by the C atom. The extra states are located at 0.10 and 4.21 eV for the C_{Al-4}+Ce_Y and distributed on the O atoms bonding with the Ce and the C atoms. The defect states at 0.15 and 2.42 eV related to the C_{Al-6}+Ce_Y are spatially located on the C atom and the O atoms belonging to surrounding YO₈ clusters. The C_i+Ce_Y creates occupied states at 0.30 and 2.24 eV devoted to the C and nearby O atoms.

Figure 4. Spin-polarized density of states for the isolated and complex Ce defects and projected charge density with a Gaussian smearing of 0.1 eV for the occupied defect states as compared to the isolated Ce defect. The top of the valence band is set to zero in the density of states. The Fermi levels are represented by the dotted lines. The isosurfaces in purple color for the charge density represent an isovalue of 0.02 e/bohr³.

3. Discussion

Following the diagrams of formation energies of the isolated and complex defects as function of the Fermi level under O-rich and O-poor limits for YAG:C presented in [9] and YAG:Ce,C obtained in this work, the defects with the lowest formation energies can be distinguished.

These positively charged defects trap electrons thus forming different F-types centers causing the strong absorption bands in as-grown crystals and are destroyed after the annealing.

Namely, at crystal growth under Ar+CO reducing conditions V_O , C_O and V_{Al} are the most probable among the isolated defects. However, the stable defects with the lowest formation energies are C_O-V_{Al-4} and C_i-Y_{Al-6} complex defects. Under air annealing, the formation energies of all the considered defects increase except those of $C_{Al}-V_O$, C_O-V_{Al} , and C_i-V_{Al-6} .

These defects are stabilized in -3 and -4 oxidation states and do not capture electrons: no color centers are formed.[9]

In case of Ce-doping, positively charged C_O-Ce_Y and negatively charged $C_{Al}-Ce_Y$ have the lowest formation energies in O-poor conditions, whereas $C_{Al}-Ce_Y$ with the -3 charge is the most favorable defect after annealing in air. Similar to Ce-free YAG:C, no stable charged defects exist after the annealing except Ce^{4+} defects, while such negatively charged defects at the same time may trap holes and provide more efficient carrier transport to Ce_Y luminescence centers. This creates conditions for transport of electrons and holes to such complex defects, which may be illustrated on the example of Ce_Y-C_{Al-6} (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. A proposed scheme of the carrier transport to luminescence centers in YAG:Ce,C scintillator on the example of Ce_Y-C_{Al-6} complex defect.

This mechanism may be similar to that proposed by Blahuta et al. ^[10] and Nikl et al. ^[11-16] for Ce-doped complex oxides co-doped with divalent cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}). Following these works, Ce^{3+} is partially converted into the tetravalent state to compensate the excessive negative charge induced by the substitution of trivalent host ions with a divalent dopant. In the scintillation process, Ce^{4+} immediately captures electron thus forming excited Ce^{3+*} , which then transfers to the ground state with emission of scintillation photons. Then Ce^{3+} captures hole and returns to the 4+ state, herein holes from the valence band are captured by a hole trapped at an O^{2-} ion perturbed by a defect, most probably a divalent impurity ion situated nearby Ce^{4+} .^[13] Mg^{2+} -antisite ion hole traps prevent the antisite defects from participating in electron trapping, thus enhancing the scintillation efficiency.^[14] The negatively charged $C_{Al}-Ce_Y$ defects may act similar way to divalent codoping and enhance scintillation efficiency in YAG:Ce,C crystals. On the other hand, in the Ce-doped crystals, the O^- hole centers may have a positive effect.^[13, 14] First, the holes stored at these oxygen ions situated near carbon-doped defects stabilize and dynamically restore the Ce^{4+} centers, which provides an additional fast recombination pathway in the scintillation mechanism. Note that the dramatic decrease in the averaged C-O bond length near $C_{Al-4}+Ce_Y$ defects evidences a strong influence of the discussed O^- centers by carbon atoms. It's worth noting that in

contrast to doping with divalent cations,^[15, 16] no luminescence quenching and acceleration of luminescence decay has been observed in YAG:Ce,C. Obviously, mechanisms of energy transfer in carbon-doped scintillators needs more detailed study.

Previously we have shown that there are at least 10 absorption bands that can be attributed to color centers are manifested in as-grown YAG:C.^[9] Comparing the spectra obtained from different parts of YAG:C with presumably low and high carbon concentrations, one may note that sample with a lower carbon concentration contains “conventional” color centers related, more probably, to oxygen vacancies with absorption in the visible band (**Figure 6a**) and no visible emission. At higher carbon concentration, the formation of F⁺-centers disturbed by Y_{Al} antisite defects^[17, 18] and/or the mentioned carbon-related defects is more favorable that results in the appearance of a clear absorption band at 368 nm (**Figure 6a**) and emission bands peaked around 400 and 650 nm (**Figure 6b**). While the 400 nm peak was often reported in literature (see, for ex. ^[18]), the 650 nm peak, at our best knowledge, has not been mentioned. The relation of these peaks to F⁺-centers is evidenced by the fast luminescence decay of 3 ns (400 nm band) and 11 ns (650 nm band) at intrinsic excitation (**Figure 6c**). Ce-doping (these spectra are not shown) does not affect the presence/absence of the mentioned absorption and emission bands.

Figure 6. Absorption spectra of YAG:C crystals with a high and low carbon content (a); excitation and emission spectra (b) and decay curves (c) of YAG:C crystal with a high carbon content.

4. Conclusion

The present study evidences an important role of carbon-related centers in the scintillation process in YAG:C and YAG:Ce,C crystals. While the positively charged defects favor the formation of F-type centers in as-grown crystals, the annealing in air favors the formation of tetravalent cerium, while the remained negatively charged defects may enhance the hole transport to Ce luminescence centers. The presented calculations do not consider more complex defects, for example, $C_{Al}-V_O-Ce_Y$, which may be favorable basing on the stability of $C_{Al}-V_O$ defects in YAG:C: such calculations need much longer computational time, although the mechanism of electron and hole capture in them should be similar to that described on the example of less complex defects. Meanwhile, selective spectroscopy, thermal- and optical stimulated luminescence, and EPR studies would enhance our understanding of the scintillation mechanisms in carbon-doped garnets.

5. Methods

5.1. Theoretical method

All the total energy calculations were performed in the framework of density functional theory and the projector augmented wave method, as implemented in Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package.^[19] The generalized gradient approximation proposed by Perdew, Burke, and Ernzerhof is included in exchange-correlation potential.^[20] The energy cutoff for plane-wave basis is set to be 400 eV. The total energy converges to 10^{-6} eV in the iterative solution of Kohn-Sham equation. Stability of defects is investigated in supercells containing $2 \times 2 \times 2$ unit cells. A k-mesh of $3 \times 3 \times 3$ is used for the Brillouin zone integration. All structures are relaxed until the residual forces on the atoms have declined to less than 0.01 eV \AA^{-1} .

The formation energies determined by total energies of different systems and atomic chemical potentials in YAG:C have been discussed in our previous paper.^[9] In this paper, the chemical potential of Ce is subject to

$$\mu_{\text{Ce}} + 2 \cdot \mu_{\text{O}} = E(\text{CeO}_2) \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_{\text{Ce}} \leq E(\text{Ce}). \quad (2)$$

The O-rich and O-poor limits refer to the upper and lower boundaries of O chemical potential, which can be tuned in the experiments.

The isolated substitutional Ce at the Y site (Ce_Y) defect and four types of carbon-containing defects near cerium occupying Y site were considered (other possible occupations of Ce were disregarded): carbon at the oxygen site $\text{C}_O + \text{Ce}_Y$, in interstitial $\text{C}_i + \text{Ce}_Y$, and at two inequivalent aluminum sites $\text{C}_{\text{Al-4}} + \text{Ce}_Y$, $\text{C}_{\text{Al-6}} + \text{Ce}_Y$ (**Figure 1**). **The structure contained 160 atoms in total.**

5.2. Crystal growth and characterization

YAG and YAG:Ce crystals were grown by the Czochralski method in Mo or W crucibles under Ar+CO atmosphere (the growth procedure is described elsewhere^[21]). The samples for optical measurements were cut from crack-free parts of the boules in the shape of $5 \times 5 \times 1$ mm plates with the 5×5 polished faces. Absorption spectra in UV-VIS regions were recorded by

SPECORD 40 (Analytic Jena) spectrophotometer. Luminescence and decay kinetic studies were carried out at 300K using a combined fluorescent lifetime and steady-state spectrometer FLS 920 (Edinburgh Instruments) equipped with xenon Xe 450W lamp for steady-state measurements and hydrogen filled nF 900 nanosecond flashlamp (optical pulse duration is 1.0–1.6 ns, pulse repetition rate is 40 kHz) for time correlated single photon counting measurements. Excitation spectra were corrected on the incident photon flux. Emission spectra were corrected for the spectral sensitivity of the detection system.

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Table of Contents (ToC)

The paper addresses the features of carbon-related defects in YAG and YAG:Ce crystals. Ab-initio calculations of defect formation energies and charged states were performed in combination with optical characterization of crystals. A scheme of enhanced energy transfer to Ce luminescence centers involving the carbon-related defects is proposed.

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